

THE EXPRESSION AND USAGE OF PUN IN STYLISTIC FIELD

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We know that Pun is included to a type of lexical stylistic device, which all on Interaction of Primary and Derivative Logical Meanings of the words. However, while investigating some information about pun, we can see that few researches and investigations were carried in this field. These researches show that the pun has a special role in English language and it adds additional meaning and humor to the speech of the speaker. It makes the language colorful and meaningful. In this article, we are going to investigate the role of pun in the English language.

Some scholars define pun as a wordplay. For example, Leppihalme states that wordplay can be based on several different features of the language(s) involved. These features are pronunciation, spelling, morphology, vocabulary or syntax.

According to its form, wordplay can be expressed in ambiguous verbal wit, orthographic peculiarities, sounds and forms of the words, in breaking the grammar rules and other linguistic factors. It should be also mentioned that context has a vital importance for the actualization of the wordplay (pun), as its pragmatic role (mainly humorous, satirical, sarcastic, etc) is fulfilled and actualized in a specific context. It is obvious that there is not a universal definition of wordplay or pun; that the difficulties created by the complexity of wordplay and its various classifications are caused by the complexity of the phenomenon and its categories and subcategories. As a result of different perceptions and understanding of wordplay there are also various approaches as to how it should be classified. As it is known, there is not a consensus among scholars on the difference between a wordplay and a pun. Delabastita and Gothlib consider these two terms mostly interchangeable and synonymous elements.¹

I do not follow their opinions and consider pun as one of the types of wordplay, whereas wordplay is classed as an umbrella term denoting all the subclasses, such as spoonerism, malapropism, wellerism, onomatopoeia, palindrome and other linguistic units. Thus, wordplay can be discussed in its

¹ (Dirk Delabastita, 1996 "Wordplay & Translation" St. Jerome Publishing .

narrow and broad senses. The pun, also called paronomasia, is a form of wordplay which suggests two or more meanings, by exploiting multiple meanings of words, or of similar-sounding words, for an intended humorous or rhetorical effect. Henri Bergson defines a pun as a sentence or utterance in which "the same sentence appears to offer two independent meanings, but it is only an appearance; in reality there are two different sentences made up of different words, but claiming to be one and the same because both have the same sound". As John Dryden puts it, punning is to torture one poor word ten thousand ways. (Dryden's quotes). Walter Redfern succinctly says: "To pun is to treat homonyms as synonyms".² Considering the above mentioned definitions and the study of empirical material, we can come to the conclusion and say that the pun is a figure of speech which consists of a deliberate confusion of similar words or phrases for rhetorical effect, whether humorous or serious. So humorous or any other effects created by puns depend upon the ambiguities words entail.

Classification of pun in the English language

The homophonic pun, a common type, utilizes the exploitation of word pairs which sound alike (homophones) but are not synonymous. Walter Redfern exemplified this type with his statement "To pun is to treat homonyms as synonyms". For example, in George Carlin's phrase "Atheism is a non-prophet institution", the word "prophet" is put in place of its homophone "profit", inverting the common phrase "non-profit institution". Similarly, the joke "Question: Why do we still have troops in Germany? Answer: To keep the Russians in Czech" relies on the aural ambiguity of the homophones "check" and "Czech".

A homographic pun exploits words which are spelled the same (homographs) but possess different meanings and sounds. Because of their nature, they rely on sight more than hearing, contrary to homophonic puns. They are also known as heteronymic puns. Examples in which the punned words typically exist in two different parts of speech often rely on unusual sentence construction, as in the anecdote: "When asked to explain his large number of children, the pig answered simply: 'The wild oats of my sow gave us many piglets.'" An example which combines homophonic and homographic punning would be Douglas Adams's line "You can tune a guitar, but you can't tuna fish."

Homonymic puns, another common type, arise from the exploitation of words which are both homographs and homophones. The statement "Being in politics is just like playing golf: you are trapped in one bad lie after another" puns

² **Puns**. Author: W D Redfern. Publisher: Oxford : Blackwell, 1984

on the two meanings of the word lie as “a deliberate untruth” and as “the position in which something rests”. An adaptation of a joke repeated by Isaac Asimov gives us “Did you hear about the little moron who strained himself while running into the screen door?”, playing on ‘strained’ as “to give much effort” and “to filter”.

A **compound pun** is a statement that contains two or more puns. For example, a complex statement by Richard Whitely includes four puns: “Why can a man never starve in the Great Desert? Because he can eat the sand which is there. But what brought the sandwiches there? Why, Noah sent Ham, and his descendants mustered and bred.” This pun uses “sand which is there/sandwiches there, “Ham/ham”, “mustered/mustard”, and “bred/bread”. Compound puns may also combine two phrases that share a word. For example, “Where do mathematicians go on weekends? To a Möbius strip club!” puns on Möbius strip and strip club. There is no generally accepted definition of a double or other multiple puns, although George Carlin claimed to pen a double pun in a lewd joke in *You Are All Diseased*.

A **recursive pun** is one in which the second aspect of a pun relies on the understanding of an element in the first. For example the statement “ π is only half a pie.” (π radians is 180 degrees, or half a circle, and a pie is a complete circle). Another example is “Infinity is not infinity,” which means infinity is not in finite range, (infinity can be split up as in finity). Another example is “A Freudian slip is when you say one thing but mean your mother.” Finally, we are given “Immanuel doesn't pun, he Kant” by Oscar Wilde. Richard J. Alexander notes two additional forms which puns may take: graphological puns, such as concrete poetry; and morphological puns, such as portmanteaus.

Visual puns are used in many logos, emblems, insignia, and other graphic symbols, in which one or more of the pun aspects are replaced by a picture. In European heraldry, this technique is called canting arms. Visual and other puns and word games are also common in Dutch gable stones as well as in some cartoons, such as *Lost Consonants* and *The Far Side*. Another type of visual pun exists in languages which use non-phonetic writing. For example, in Chinese, a pun may be based on a similarity in shape of the written character, despite a complete lack of phonetic similarity in the words punned upon. Mark Elvin describes how this “peculiarly Chinese form of visual punning involved comparing written characters to objects.”

Comedy and jokes

Puns are a common source of humour in jokes and comedy shows. They are often used in the punch line of a joke, where they typically give a humorous

meaning to a rather perplexing story. These are also known as feghoots. One practitioner of using puns in a comedic context is the British comedian Andy Zaltzman, co-host of the popular political podcast, *The Bugle* with John Oliver who becomes increasingly aghast the longer Zaltzman goes on. Zaltzman once created a string of 31 dog-related puns in a row in episode 117 of “*The Bugle*.” Another practitioner of this art is René Goscinny, co-creator of *Asterix*. The following example comes from the movie *Master and Commander: The Far Side of the World*, though the punchline stems from far older Vaudeville roots. The final line puns on the stock phrase “the lesser of two evils”.

Captain Aubrey: “Do you see those two weevils, Doctor?...Which would you choose?”

Dr. Maturin: “Neither. There's not a scrap of difference between them. They're the same species of *Curculio*.”

Captain Aubrey: “If you had to choose. If you were forced to make a choice. If there were no other option.”

Dr. Maturin: “Well, then, if you're going to push me. I would choose the right-hand

weevil. It has significant advantage in both length and breadth.”

Captain Aubrey: “There, I have you!...Do you not know that in the Service, one must always choose the lesser of two weevils?”

The last line uses a pun on the stock phrase “the lesser of two evils”.

The usage of pun in literature

Non-humorous puns were and are a standard rhetorical and poetic device in English literature. Puns and other forms of word play have been used by many famous writers, such as Alexander Pope, James Joyce, Vladimir Nabokov, Robert Bloch, Lewis Carroll, John Donne, and William Shakespeare, who is estimated to have used over 3,000 puns in his plays.

Here is an example from Shakespeare's *Richard III*:

“Now is the winter of our discontent made glorious summer by this son of York” (Son/sun).

Shakespeare was also noted for his frequent play with less serious puns, the “quibbles” of the sort that made Samuel Johnson complain, “A quibble is to Shakespeare what luminous vapours are to the traveller! He follows it to all adventures; it is sure to lead him out of his way, sure to engulf him in the mire. It has some malignant power over his mind, and its fascinations are irresistible.” Elsewhere, Johnson disparagingly referred to punning as “the lowest form of humour”.

In the poem *A Hymn to God the Father*, John Donne, married to Anne More, reportedly puns repeatedly on his own name (which is pronounced “Dun”). “Son/sun” in the second quoted line, and two compound puns on “Donne/done” and “More/more”. All three are homophonic, with the puns on “more” being both homographic and capitonymic. The ambiguities serve to introduce several possible meanings into the verses.

“When Thou hast done, Thou hast not done/For I have more”.

Can be interpreted as “God, when you have forgiven me this much, you are not finished/you do not have John Donne (safe yet), for I have more sins to confess”. In the third stanza, having received assurance, counteracting his fears,

“that at my death Thy Son/ Shall shine as he shines now, and heretofore”
(another Son/sun pun), he ends the poem

“And having done that, Thou hast done; I fear no more”.

Here are some additional examples:

“As different as York from Leeds” - James Joyce in *Finnegans Wake*

(A play on the idiomatic expression “As different as chalk from cheese”.)

On the other hand, puns are despised by some authors and critics as being too “vulgar” or “childish”. For example, Samuel Johnson once gave the definition “Pun (n.): the lowest form of humour”. Also, some puns in Literature take the form of place names or character’s names. For example in the Harry Potter series, the alleyways with the names “Diagon Alley” and “Knockturn Alley” are puns for “Diagonally” and “Nocturnally”, respectively. Multiple puns like these can be found everywhere in literature.

Mostkova points out that Pun (It. Puntiglio ‘fine point’)-Каламбур The humorous or ludicrous use of a word in more than one sense; a play on words. The Fool’s speech in Shakespeare’s *King Lear* is rich in puns.³

E.g:

FOOL. Give me an egg, nuncle, and I’ll give three two crowns.

LEAR. What two crowns shall they be?

FOOL. Why, after I have cut the egg i’ the middle and eat up the meat, the two crowns of the egg. When thou clovest thy crown i’ the middle and gavest away both parts, thou borest thine ass on thy back o’er the dirt: thou hadst little wit in thy

bald crown when thou gavest thy golden one away.

³ Мосткова. Английская литературоведческая терминология. Издательство “Просвещение” ленинградское отделение ленинград. 1967, Р. 74

Here the pun is based on the following meanings of the word crown: 'a coin', 'an egg-shell', 'king's crown', 'the top of one's head'.

Another example of pun can be found in Hilaire Belloc's epigram on his books:

"When I am dead, I hope it may be said":

"His sins were scarlet, but his books were read".

Here the pun is based on two homophones, read and red.

V. A. Kukhareno points out that Pun - the role of the context is similar to that of zeugma, while the structure is changed, for the central word is repeated.⁴

I. R. Galperin points out that Pun is another stylistic device based on the interaction of two well-known meanings of a word or phrase. It is difficult to draw a hard and fast distinction between zeugma and the pun. The only reliable distinguishing feature is a structural one: zeugma is the realization of two meanings with the help of a verb which is made to refer to different subjects or objects (direct or indirect). The pun is more independent. There need not necessarily be a word in the sentence to which the pun-word refers. This does not mean, however, that the pun is entirely free. Like any other stylistic device, it must depend on a context. But the context may be of a more expanded character, sometimes even as large as a whole work of emotive prose. Thus the title of one of Oscar Wilde's plays, "The Importance of Being *Earnest*" has a pun in it, inasmuch as the name of the hero and the adjective meaning 'seriously-minded' are both present in our mind.⁵

Here is another example of a pun where a larger context for its realization is used:

"*Bow to the board*", said Bumble. Oliver brushed away two or three tears that were lingering in his eyes; and *seeing no board but the table*, fortunately *bowed to that*". (Dickens)

Puns are often used in riddles and jokes, for example, in this riddle: what is the difference between a schoolmaster and an engine-driver? (One trains the mind and the other minds the train.)

Devices of simultaneously realizing the various meanings of words, which are of a more subtle character than those embodied in puns and zeugma, are to be found in poetry and poetical descriptions and in speculations in emotive prose. Men-of-letters are especially sensitive to the nuances of meaning embodied in almost every common word, and to make these words live with their multifarious

⁴ V. A. Kukhareno. *Seminars In Style*. Higher School Publishing House. Moscow, 1971, P.26

⁵ I. R. Galperin. *Stylistics*. Moscow "Higher School", 1977, P.151.

semantic aspects is the task of a good writer. Those who can do it easily are said to have talent.

To illustrate the interplay of primary and contextual meanings, let us take a few examples from poetical works:

In Robert Frost's poem "Stopping by Woods on a Snowy Evening" the poet, taking delight in watching the snow fall on the woods, concludes his poem in the following words:

"The woods are lovely, dark and deep.

But I have promises to keep,

And miles to go before I sleep,

And miles to go before I sleep."

The word 'promises' here is made to signify two concepts, *viz.* 1) a previous engagement to be fulfilled and 2) moral or legal obligation.

The plural form of the word as well as the whole context of the poem are convincing proof that the second of the two meanings is the main one, in spite of the fact that in combination with the verb *to keep* (to keep a promise) the first meaning is more predictable.

Here is another example.

In Shakespearian Sonnet 29 there are the following lines:

"When in disgrace with fortune and men's eyes,

I all alone beweep my outcast state,

And trouble deaf heaven with my bootless cries

And think upon myself and curse my fate".

Almost every word here may be interpreted in different senses: sometimes the differences are hardly perceptible, sometimes they are obviously antagonistic to the primary meaning.

However, we shall confine our analysis only to the meaning of the word 'cries' which signifies both prayer and lamentation. These two meanings are suggested by the relation of the word 'cries' to 'trouble deaf heaven'. But the word 'cries' suggests not only prayer and lamentation, it also implies violent prayer and lamentation as if in deep despair, almost with tears (see the word 'beweep' in the second line of the part of the sonnet quoted).

It is very important to be able to follow the author's intention from his manner of expressing nuances of meaning which are potentially present in the semantic structure of existing words. Those who fail to define the suggested meanings of poetic words will never understand poetry because they are unable to decode the poetic language.

In various functional styles of language the capacity of a word to signify several meanings simultaneously manifests itself in different degrees.

To sum up, the research shows that, puns used in the examples of the given article are created on the basis of syntactic, semantic, structural and lexical ambiguity. Wordplay and its categories are changeable expressive means and together with the development of languages, new types are formed and developed. However, because of its interesting nature, wordplay and its categories will always be of the central interest for scholars. Additionally, puns are used to create humor and sometimes require a large vocabulary to understand. Puns have long been used by comedy writers, such as William Shakespeare, Oscar Wilde, and George

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